

NATURAL FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER BIOCOMPOSITES AND BLENDS: SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND APPLICATIONS.

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KEY WORDS: Betel Nut Fiber, Composites, Blends, SEM, TEM.

SUMMARY

. Polymer natural fibers blends and composites are replacing a number of conventional plastic materials. Betel nut fiber is extracted from the seeds and their composites and blends are prepared with synthetic polymer. Finally their properties and applications were studied with the help of different sophisticated analytical instruments.

KEY WORDS: *Betel nut fiber, Blends, Composites, Biowaste, Biodegradable, Areca catechu.*

INTRODUCTION

Natural fibers are being increasingly used as reinforcement in polymer composites and blends primarily due to their low cost, low density and good sets of mechanical properties. A huge quantity of biowaste such as betel nut (*Areca catechu*) fiber is found unutilized. The present work reports the use of this rural biowaste, for the first time, as reinforcement in developing polymer composites and blends. The search for more durable and ecologically sound materials is very prominent in a process of technological change that is enveloping the industry. Natural fiber offer many technological and environmental benefits when used to reinforce composites such as high strength and stiffness quality in low density materials. [1-3]

Betel nut fiber (*Areca nut hush fiber*) is characterized as extremely strong and light weight. The fibers are predominantly composed of cellulose and varying proportions of hemi cellulose, lignin, pectin and protopectin. Natural fibers are replacing glass fiber in many applications and are achieving equal strength, increased flexibility and low weight. These fibers have special advantages in comparison to other synthetic fiber in that they are abundantly available from a renewable resource and also biodegradable. At the same time they have low density, high toughness and acceptable specific strength properties and good thermal property. The fiber is alkali treated for better result. [4-5].

Polymer natural fiber blends and composites are of two types, miscible and immiscible. When two polymers are blended together they generally create their own matrix-reinforcement partnership, whereby the majority constituent forms a homogeneous matrix in which the minority constituent is dispersed. Just as in ordinary composites, the quality of this dispersion, as well as the strength of matrix-reinforcement interface is determining factors in the mechanical properties of the materials. [6-8]

The mechanical and surface properties of betel nut fiber are somewhat unknown. Investigation into physical and mechanical properties is needed to determine suitable fiber treatment and manufacturing methods, in order to optimize the properties of betel nut fiber reinforced composites. The development of betel nut fiber reinforced composite material as a replacement for synthetic plastic provides three key advantages:

1. Utilization of an abundant supply of betel nut fiber, thereby providing economic benefit to poor rural people.
2. Reducing the existing dependency on nonrenewable resources
3. Reducing plastic waste and associated harmful substances from the process of plastic incinerations.

The adhesion between the natural fiber and the polymer matrix can be increased by modifying the fiber surface. Chemical treatment by removing organic residue from the surface of the fiber can also enhance the adhesion because the surface of natural fiber is coarse in structure and thus, enable an interlocking mechanism with the matrix. [9-10].

The current work is an attempt to use betel nut fiber as reinforcement for block copolymer composites. The composite was fabricated using simple technique.

EXPERIMENTAL

1 Raw materials: In the preparation of synthetic polymers, the monomers 4-hydroxy benzaldehyde [HBD], 4,4' diamino diphenyl ether [DDE] , terephthaloyl chloride [TTC] were obtained from Merck Limited Germany. The solvent Dimethyl Sulfoxide [DMSO] and Triethyl amine catalyst were obtained from SISCO Mumbai.

.2 Synthesis of polymer:

Polymer: The polymer was prepared by mixing 2.44 gm [0.02 mol] 4-hydroxy benzaldehyde and 4 gm [0.02 moles] Diamino diphenyl ether mixture in a four necked round bottom flask. 40 ml DMSO as solvent and 2 ml conc. H₂SO₄ as condensing agent were added. The mass was stirred with a magnetic stirrer and heated at 80⁰ C in nitrogen atmosphere for 4 hours. The mixture was then cooled and 4.06 gm [0.02 mole] Terephthaloyl chloride , 20 ml DMSO, 2ml Triethyl amine were added and again heated at 80⁰ C for 4 hours in the atmosphere of nitrogen with constant stirring . Finally the polymer was precipitated in water, filtered and dried in an oven at 100⁰ C. Finally it is purified.

3 Extraction of Fiber: Ripe betel nut fruit is kept under water for several days and then seed is removed. The fiber is mechanically removed from the seeds. It is then washed with water, refluxed with 2 % alkali and then washed with very dilute acid to remove unreacted alkali. It is completely dried in the oven at 120⁰ C for 24 hours and powdered mechanically for the preparation of composites and blends.

4. Characterization of fiber and polymer:

FT-IR Study:

The polymer sample was prepared in the form of pellets with KBr. The FT-IR data were recorded using KBr pellets in FT-IR Spectro Photometer [Impact 410].

¹H – NMR Analysis

¹H-NMR data was recorded at 250 MHz Bruker NMR spectrometer using DMSO [d₆] and CDCl₃

Thermal Analysis

[A] Thermo gravimetric Analysis: Thermo Gravimetric Analysis [TGA] was performed on a Mettler Toledo Star System under Nitrogen atmosphere at the heating rate of 10⁰C / min.

[B] Differential Scanning Calorimetry: Differential Scanning Calorimetric [DSC] studies were carried on a Mettler Toledo Star Thermal Analyzer under Nitrogen atmosphere at the heating rate of 10⁰C/ min.

SEM Analysis

Scanning Electron Micrographs [SEM] were obtained by JEOL JSM 6360 LV high-resolution scanning electron microscope. The samples were sputter coated with a layer of homogenous gold to facilitate dissipation of charge during imaging.

Methods of Preparation of Blends and composites:

The polymer is dissolved in DMSO and heated with different percentage of fiber for 30 minutes with constant magnetic stirring. Then the solvent is removed. The composites were prepared to investigate different properties. The first group of sample was prepared with carefully measured volume fractions at 10, 20 and 30% fiber respectively.

Results and Discussion

¹HNMR Analysis: The HNMR spectra of polymer where characteristic peaks were observed at 8 ppm for aromatic proton, 9.7 ppm for proton of –CH=N-, 6.8-7 ppm for proton of –CONH- group.

This shows that the polymer is synthesized correctly. Moreover the formation of the polymer is further confirmed by FT-IR analysis, viscosity determination, and molecular weight determination by GPC analysis. The graphs and datas are not given due space problem.

Actually we have synthesized a number of polymers for the preparation of blends and composites with betel nut fiber. Their physical and mechanical properties are being studied by our group. We are also studying their different applications in divers fields.

4.3 Thermal Analysis: From the TGA and DSC study of the polymer, fiber and the composites it is clear that thermal stability of the composites is much higher. Among the composites 20 % shows the best result

Fig 2 a DSC of Polymer

Fig.2 b DSC of Polymer Composite I

Fig 2 c DSC of Composite I I

Fig 2 d DSC of Polymer

Fig 2 e DSC of Composite I

Fig 2 f DSC of Composite II

4.4 SEM Analysis of Blends and Composites:

From SEM study, it is found that the alkaline treatment of the fiber effectively cleans the fiber surface and increases the fiber surface roughness. It shows that there is correct interaction between the constituent materials. The morphology of the composites revealed efficient fiber-matrix adhesion. The micrograph exhibit a two phase system showing betel nut fiber dispersed in polymer matrix.

Fig: 3 a, SEM of Betel nut fiber

Fig: 3 b, SEM of betel fiber and polymer composite

5. CONCLUSION: The primary achievement of this work has been the demonstration that betel nut fiber block copolymer composites are suitable for many applications. We have successfully synthesized a new class of composite materials. Limited attempts have been made so far for the processing, characterization of these composites. However this is important since they generate employment in both rural and urban areas, in addition to helping in reducing waste whereby it contributes to healthy environment. We feel more studies are required on product development and their performance evaluation.

It can be concluded that a low cost polymer betel nut composites can be processed utilizing a bio-waste and thereby reducing the level of environmental pollution. Their mechanical and physical properties are being studied by our group.

Applications: Betel nut (*Areca nut*) fibers can be exploited commercially for the production of furnishing fabrics, textiles, etc by blending with cotton, viscose and polyester. They can be used in automobiles, railway, aerospace, military applications, building and construction industries, packaging, consumer products etc. Further work is now in hand to commercialize this product. Attention should also be paid to develop easy and effective processing methods for these materials to make them more amenable to industrial applications. The present work demonstrated that betel nut fiber can be used as excellent reinforcing material for low cost composites and are able to satisfy economical as well as ecological interest.

Acknowledgement

We thank the authority of Cotton College, Guwahati, Tezpur University, IIT Guwahati, NEHU Shillong and Assam University Silchar for the use of their Library and Laboratory facilities.

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